

Conductometric Study of Thallium(I) Chelates of 3,4-Dihydroxy- and 3,4,5-Trihydroxy-benzoic Acids

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Thallium (I) forms 1:1 chelates with 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic (protocatechuic) and 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic (gallie) acids. The composition has been established by monovariation and Job's continued variation methods. The dissociation constants determined by the latter method at 28°, are 41.83×10^{-4} and 27.87×10^{-4} for thalious-protocatechuate and thalious-gallate chelate respectively.

3,4-Dihydroxybenzoate and 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoate chelates of only Mo, W, V, Sn, Bi¹ and boron² have been studied so far. In the present investigation, the authors have studied the reaction of these ligands with thalious nitrate. Literature indicates that chelates are more stable in alkaline than in acidic medium. Sodium salts of protocatechuic and gallie acids were therefore chosen as ligands.

EXPERIMENTAL

E. Merck sample of thalious nitrate and B. D. H. samples of anhydrous sodium carbonate, protocatechuic acid and gallie acid were used in this investigation.

Conductivity readings were recorded using "Doron" conductivity bridge with WTW 1000-cycle oscillator and dip-type conductivity cell. All measurements were made at 28°.

DISCUSSION

The stoichiometry of the chelates were determined by monovariation method³ and Job's continued variation method⁴ for equimolar solutions. By both the methods it has been concluded that Na-protocatechuate and Na-gallate form 1:1 chelates with thalious nitrate. The dissociation constants, determined by continued variation method for non-equimolar solutions, are 41.83×10^{-4} and 27.87×10^{-4} for thalious-protocatechuate and thalious-gallate chelate respectively. Composition by monovariation method is shown in Fig. 1 and that by continued variation in Fig. 2; dissociation is shown in Fig. 3.

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1. *Ann. Acad. Sci. Fennicae*, 1959, *Sec. AII*, No. 96, p. 64.

2. Khan and Sen, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1959, **49A**, 226.

3. Nayar and Pande, *Ibid.*, 1949, **27A**, 284.

4. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, *x*, 9, 113.

Action of Sodium Hydroxide.—Both the ligands were mixed with the metal solution in 1:1 ratio and after the attainment of equilibrium titrated against an equimolar solution of NaOH. In the graph of conductance against the volume of NaOH, it has been observed that a clear break is obtained at the point where the volume of NaOH is equal to the volume of equimolar ligand solution present in the mixture. This confirms

Ml of (A = M/30) Na-gallate and (B = M/40) of Na-protocat. added to 5 ml of similar strength of $TiNO_3$.

FIG. 1.

% Ligand.

FIG. 2

A and B represent respectively M/30 and M/40 equimol. soln. of $TiNO_3$ and Na-gallate. A' and B'—M/30 and M/40 of $TiNO_3$ and Na-protocat.

that in both the ligands only one hydroxyl group is taking part in the chelate formation, and perhaps it is the -OH group nearer to the -COOH group being more reactive as compared to other -OH groups.

% Ligand.

FIG. 3

A = M/25, B = M/50 Na-gallate with M/100- $TiNO_3$.
A' = M/25, B' = M/50-Na-protocat. with N/100- $TiNO_3$.

Thallous-protocatechuate.—The colour of Na-protocatechuate solution is yellow before as well as after the chelate formation. The chelate in solution therefore is a colorless one. The co-ordination positions in thallous ion, not satisfied by ligand ion, are therefore satisfied by water molecules. The probable structure of thallous-protocatechuate chelate is represented by (I).

Thallous-gallate.—Na-gallate solution is blue in colour. When thallous nitrate solution is gradually added to it, the colour of the mixture becomes more

and more intense and it is darkest when the metal and the ligand solutions in the mixture are 50% each. After that the colour gradually fades. It shows that the colour of the complex ion is also blue, which intensifies the blue colour of Na-gallate solution. Nitron solution completely precipitates the nitrate ion present in the 1:1 (metal: ligand) mixture, showing that the nitrate ion is not taking part in the complex formation. The structure of thallos-gallate chelate can therefore be assigned as (II):

From the dissociation constants of the two chelates it is observed that thallos-gallate is more stable than thallos-protocatechuate. This is probably due to the more basic character of gallic acid as compared to protocatechuic acid caused by the introduction of one more -OH group in the structure of protocatechuic acid.

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